

Skyhook and Groundhook Control for a Robotic Semi-Active Suspension

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1 Introduction

Autonomous mobile platforms require precise control over vertical vibrations to maintain the accuracy of onboard equipment (sensors, cameras, manipulators), which is critical for instance in smart farming applications [1]. One of the possibilities is utilizing a semi-active suspension system based on magnetorheological (MR) dampers, offering a real-time damping coefficient modification by the magnetic field applied to the MR fluid, altering the viscosity and flow resistance [2, 3]. To exploit and assess such system's potential, this study focuses on simulation and evaluation of several control strategies.

2 Numerical model and methodology

The developed 4-wheeled robotic platform utilizing a suspension with MR dampers is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The developed platform: (a) Kinematic scheme of the independent double wishbone suspension for one wheel (two DOF - vertical movement and additional possible changing the track of wheels); (b) Dynamic numerical multibody model built in Adams software.

The shock absorber's force is defined as $\mathbf{F}_{SA} = \mathbf{F}_S + \mathbf{F}_D$, with spring's force (\mathbf{F}_S) and damper's force (\mathbf{F}_D). The latter is calculated using damper's linear velocity (\mathbf{V}_D) as $\mathbf{F}_D = b \cdot \mathbf{V}_D$. The damping coefficient b is limited to the range [1,35; 2,9] Ns/mm [1, 4]. For the wheels, the Fiala tire model was selected with parameters based on engineering standards for small pneumatic off-road tires on a moderate soil: vertical stiffness $k_z = 100\text{N/mm}$, vertical damping $\zeta = 1\text{Ns/mm}$, rolling resistance $C_r = 17\text{mm}$, friction at zero slip $U_{\max} = 0,95$, sliding friction $U_{\min} = 0,65$, longitudinal stiffness $C_s = 100\text{kN}$, cornering stiffness $C_a = 600\text{N/}^\circ$.

3 Control strategies

A proportional P-regulator was used as the initial control strategy to provide a good baseline. It sets the damping coefficient based on the chassis' centre of mass (CoM) vertical velocity's deviation from 0. The two other control strategies (on-off skyhook and groundhook) [3], utilize the full operational range of the MR damper to achieve distinct performance objectives.

The on-off skyhook control aims to maximize vertical vibration control (ride comfort) by minimizing the chassis vertical velocity $\mathbf{V}_{Y\text{chassis}}$. High damping is applied when the chassis moves away from equilibrium, which is explained in Eq. (1).

$$b_{\max} \text{ if } \mathbf{V}_{Y\text{chassis}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_D > 0 \text{ and } b_{\min} \text{ if } \mathbf{V}_{Y\text{chassis}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_D \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

The last strategy is on-off groundhook control aiming to maximize road handling by minimizing the absolute vertical velocity of the wheel $\mathbf{V}_{Y\text{wheel}}$. High damping is applied to suppress wheel separation from the road, according to the rules in Eq. (2).

$$b_{\max} \text{ if } \mathbf{V}_{Y\text{wheel}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_D < 0 \text{ and } b_{\min} \text{ if } \mathbf{V}_{Y\text{wheel}} \cdot \mathbf{V}_D \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

4 Results

Simulations were performed in Adams (2019.2) comparing the passive (constant damping $b=2,1$), P-regulator ($K_P=10^5$), on-off skyhook and groundhook cases on a sinusoidal road profile (wave height 50mm and period 1600mm). The results demonstrate the performance benefits of the semi-active suspension and especially the switching control strategies (Fig. 2). For evaluating vertical vibration control, the chassis' CoM RMS vertical acceleration (a_{RMS}) is used. For road handling stability, the dynamic tire load deviation (DTLV) [5], defined as the RMS of dynamic tire force deviation, is calculated (Table. 1).

Fig. 2. Comparative plots of dynamic response in 4 simulated cases: (a) Damping coefficient b for a chosen wheel (front right), illustrating clear switching; (b) vertical acceleration of the chassis' CoM - a_y ; (c) Vertical force F_y between the road and one wheel (FR - front right).

Table 1. Comparison of chosen numerical results (vertical vibration control and road handling metrics) for the 4 simulated cases.

Control strategy of b	a_{RMS}	DTLV for each wheel: FL – front left, FR - front right, RL- rear left, RR – rear right (N)			
1. Passive ($b=2,1$)	96,2 mm/s ²	FL 36,30 N	FR 37,54 N	RL 30,42 N	RR 29,74 N
2. P-regulator	104,8 mm/s ²	FL 35,55 N	FR 36,78 N	RL 29,78 N	RR 29,03 N
3. Skyhook	92,9 mm/s ²	FL 35,20 N	FR 36,38 N	RL 29,54 N	RR 28,84 N
4. Groundhook	105,8 mm/s ²	FL 38,06 N	FR 39,33 N	RL 31,74 N	RR 31,07 N

The P-regulator (Case 2) references the semi-active system's capabilities - damping coefficient switching in Fig. 2a. The on-off skyhook strategy isolates the chassis from road inputs, achieving the lowest a_{RMS} value (92,9mm/s²) for maximum vertical vibration control (Fig. 2b), demonstrating a reduction compared to the passive case (96,2 mm/s²). Moreover, the on-off skyhook and groundhook strategies exhibit sharp acceleration spikes caused by logical damping force discontinuities inherent to on-off control logic. The P-regulator and on-off groundhook strategies resulted in higher a_{RMS} values than the passive case, showing their reduced effectiveness in isolating vertical chassis movement (Table 1). However, lower DTLV values than the passive case (FL-36,30N), were achieved for each wheel by both the P-regulator (FL-35,55N) and the skyhook strategy (FL-35,20N), indicating improved handling stability achieved through tire contact vertical force regulation (Fig. 2c).

5 Conclusions

The research utilized the capabilities of the MR dampers force control achieving the lowest a_{RMS} for skyhook strategy. Moreover, P-regulator and skyhook cases achieved better road handling (lower DTLV) than the passive case. Results proved that a variable damping coefficient can bring benefits to a robotic wheeled vehicle, but appropriate control is crucial for correct application of semi-active suspensions. Therefore, while proving effective, the algorithms operated only at the extremes of the damping range, and the future research should use other control algorithms e.g. fuzzy logic or model predictive control [6].

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